

Evaluating The Illustrations In The Science Book For The Primary Stage According To The Scientific Picture

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<i>The current research aims to evaluate the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the scientific image, which included several criteria (10) criteria for the scientific image and appendix (1) of the science book for the sixth grade. Prepared by the researcher (the research tool), which is the (analysis tool) for the scientific illustrations and images in the book of science, which the researcher worked on preparing a list of these criteria and gave it to the experts and arbitrators in the methods. Teaching Science, Measurement and Evaluation Appendix No. (2) For the purpose of expressing their views on the validity of standards and their suitability to the level of learners and learners and how they contain scientific facts and concepts to properly transfer experiences and skills to learners in the initial stages. Standards include (matching the content of the scientific image - scientific accuracy - matching the image title - Image clarity - color accuracy - scientific image size - suitability of the image to the level of students - novelty of the image - paper type of the image - image format) All criteria for its importance in the science book were agreed upon (80%), valid. The stability and reliability of the tool were extracted according to Cooper's equation (for stability) where the reliability ratio was (0, 83), and the researcher relied on statistical methods included in frequencies. And percentages for each criterion separately, and through that the following results were obtained:</i>
Received: May 23, 2021	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>The scientific illustrations and pictures that are compatible with the standard and that were not specified against the spoken percentage drawn by the experts and arbitrators, which is (70%</i> 2. <i>Illustrations that match the content got a percentage (82, 7), while the percentage of mismatched content (17, 2), the illustrations that are characterized by this feature (scientific accuracy) got a percentage (86, 9), while they were not accurately distinguished. (13, 0), and (matching the title to the image) got (70%), while the illustrations did not match the title (30%), and so did (clarity). From the picture) the ratio was (82, 5) while it was not clear (17, 4).), etc.</i>
Accepted: December 26, 2021	<p><i>In light of this, the researcher recommended</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Focus on the principle of scientific accuracy and the use of clear color illustrations of fees.</i> 2. <i>The illustrations should fit the level of male and female learners in the primary stages.</i> <p><i>Thus, the researcher suggested</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Conducting a similar study of the current study of science books and other stages.</i> 2. <i>To conduct a study on the impact of the illustrations on the collection of secondary school students.</i>
Keywords : Calendar, Illustrations, Science Book, Scientific Picture	
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Introduction

The process of evaluating the curricula for the primary stages is a basic starting point in developing and achieving the educational goals of the teacher and the learner in order to note the strengths and weaknesses in teaching the scientific subject. The classroom and pedagogical classroom is what helps learners and students to pass the school stages and overcome the difficulties faced by both the teacher and the learner, so the researcher believes that the science book in the primary stage contains many activities, skills, knowledge, drawings and clarification of problems that help the learner to understand the scientific material in addition to applying Experiments in the classroom, in order for the learners to have many skills that help them acquire information correctly and for the purpose of building a conscious and open generation, it was decided to conduct an

evaluation study on the pictures and illustrations and the extent to which they are included in the science book at the primary stage because most science teachers suffer from recent editions looking for science books. There are many difficulties in the educational fees in the science book, activities, exercises, and teaching aids. The science book must be evaluated according to the scientific picture to overcome the difficulties related to the curriculum and put strengths and weaknesses in the specified place.

Research importance

The importance of animation and illustration comes from addressing the imagination in the first place, which is what children love. Therefore, educational institutions sought to invest in the features of animation and make it an educational tool in order to achieve a number of educational goals (Falata, 2001: 87). The scientific illustrations and images are also easy and quick to understand, and all this makes them attractive and interesting for learners in primary schools and thus the possibility of employing them in the educational process because they contribute to the development and acquisition of children. Desired values as well as help them in linguistic growth and work to achieve emotional stability for learners and redeem them. It also helps them to understand the social and economic environment (Sultana, 2005: 650). Developing the creative abilities of learners and learners is of particular importance because of its role in developing the areas of creative thinking, which in turn contributes to enhancing and revitalizing the mental abilities of learners, as creative thinking gives the learner the opportunity to achieve a number of positive results, including developing his abilities to the maximum extent possible. And prove his ability to think. Communicating and expressing what he has in mind, in addition to discovering the value of things, developing multiple skills, understanding self and others, accommodating their confidence, facing challenges, and meeting the needs of the rapidly changing world (Al-Sayed, 2013: 170). Illustrations in science books for the primary stages have a significant impact on the child's personality as one of the most important organized environmental elements that convey information, concepts and values in a sequential and narrative manner. Scientific studies indicate that out of every ten thousand children or learners, five thousand of them impersonate illustrations or cartoons. And what they're watching, and these kids come from families who don't care about their kids and aren't keen on following up on what they're seeing is a good way to give them the right information. Due to the great impact that educational fees may have, it requires countries to choose what programs they show on screens or television because it may affect the educated knowledge, its values, faith and its sound nature (Al-Nuaimi, 2003: 651). (Bokus, 2002) that learning concepts lead to linking scientific facts and clarifying the relationship in the one cognitive system and in different scientific knowledge systems. Building and selecting educational and educational activities, and that their formation and development should be one of the objectives of teaching science at all educational levels. Therefore, the study of scientific illustrations, pictures and science experiments in science books helps students to acquire scientific concepts because they are the main focus around which different science curricula revolve (Bougs, 2002). : 25).

The aim of the research

The current research aims to

(Evaluating the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the scientific picture).

Research limits

The current search is limited to:

1. Science book for the sixth grade of primary school, 2nd floor, for the academic year (2017-2018)
2. Illustrations according to the standards (scientific image)

Define terms

1- The calendar is determined by

Al-Sadiq, 2001): "It is an essential part of the educational process that includes three successive processes: measurement and evaluation, then diagnosis, and then treatment" (Al-Sadiq, 2001: 10)

Known for it Mirren, (1992) "It is a process by which the competence of employees is determined and contributions to the achievement of the tasks assigned to them are measured. Mirren, 1992: 9.

Procedural definition: "It is a judgment on the value of something".

2- Illustrations identified by both

- A. (Abu Al-Hassan, 2001): (These are successful drawings with multiple minor changes and arranged for the purpose of shooting or showing as a film) (Abu Al-Hassan, 2001: 167)
- B. (Al-Meiliji - 2006): which are the drawn materials and linear visual symbols designed to summarize, interpret and express them in a scientific manner and which are used as tools that serve the educational process of learning and teaching, and they are: difficult to understand, especially in verbal language only such as science (Al-Meiliji, 2006: 160)

Procedural definition: "It is a set of drawings, pictorial figures and scientific manuscripts in different colors that help to attract and entice male and female learners in the initial stages to obtain information correctly and facilitate the process of the lesson".

3- Book of knowledge

He defined it (Al-Tamimi, 2009): (a set of cognitive units arranged in proportion to the level of a particular class to achieve the overall growth of the learner physically, mentally, socially and spiritually, and to adapt to society in order to help teachers and learners teach them in a particular class to achieve the desired goals(“ .Al-Tamimi, 2009: 10)

Procedural definition: ("scientific content that includes a set of activities, pictures and illustrations that arouse the learner's attention and help her in achieving scientific and cognitive goals and increase her motivation towards the material and ease of understanding)

Theoretical Framework

Illustrations: Illustrations occupy a scholarly space parallel to the scholarly material. It is a visual means to clarify the scientific details of the student according to the drawn elements and shapes they contain, as well as contributing to the clearer and faster delivery of information to the student. The belief of teachers in this way of receiving information is their dependence on time that the individual perceives things which he sees better and more clearly together if he reads about them or hears talk about them in person, and that the individual can obtain the greatest amount of his experiences through the senses of hearing and sight (ulnar, 2014; 294). The educational study such as the study (Kashik 2003) showed that the educated and the uneducated get 98% of the illustrations and are moved by the senses of hearing and sight, and this percentage learns (90%) almost through the sense of sight, while (8%) through the hearing, as they did not. The mass media and television are a means of media communication, but have effectively and effectively exceeded that in the educational fields, especially for children and in a broader sense. Adults: as a pedagogical aid that combines the senses of hearing and sight, and this helps to fix the information in the memory of the young viewer (Kishek, 2003: 4). While (Rashid, 2002) mentions that pictures and educational graphics help learners to communicate with and identify their environment and the world around them and bring the same reality closer to them. Studies and research in this field reveal that using pictures and graphics with written oral materials is better than using only written materials, and that it helps to retain the information provided for longer periods, as it applies scientific ideas in everyday situations, making it attractive and easy for learners of all ages. It is also used to enhance and consolidate a simplified understanding of science and has useful uses in the classroom through the presentation of lessons and works to educate and educate the learner, and this gives enough motivation to use this method that is used well in various educational and social fields. Economic, health and other fields that include many of the knowledge, skills, and sciences that individuals want to learn and have access to (Rashid, 2002: 6).

The importance of illustrations in the science book

Illustrations and education gained their importance by being visual aids and this made them prefer many means because the individual perceives things he sees better than if he reads or hears them, and the importance of illustrations can be expressed as follows:

1. Provides information in visual information.
2. Giving the student the opportunity to think deductively.
3. Arouse student interest and standardize information.

Conditions to be fulfilled in the illustrations

1. Draw a link to the lesson objectives.
2. The drawing is commensurate with the level of the students.
3. Graphical content link.
4. The honesty and realism of the drawing.
5. Coordination of colors, with the need to draw clear parts.
6. The drawing contains correct and specific information.
7. The size of the fee is proportional to the number of students (Asqal, 2002: 51)

Al-Husari (2004) finds that despite the scientific images and illustrations in textbooks, these drawings do not get enough attention from the learners as do the oral texts in the books, and he points out that the learners do not tend to look at the images and drawings. Graphics. Graphics. They obtain information through their reading of written texts, that the book and test questions relate to the scientific material covered by the oral texts and not to the illustrations, meanings and ideas they address, and that these questions may require the learner to answer. It is verbal or restricted to a measure of the learner's ability and skill in redrawing the visual figures he has studied previously. Perhaps the reason students are not interested in illustrations is because of the pictorial questions that deal with these drawings (Al-Husari, 2004: 460) and educational studies of illustrative behavior in science books such as the study (Abdullah, 2002). The effectiveness of graphs and caricatures as types of illustrations has been reconstructed because they achieve the objectives of the proposed unit in social studies, taking into account the design of images and graphics according to the usual standards, and helped to obtain them. Knowledge has become easier and easier than ever before, according to a study (Barakat and Khuza'a 2008) that focused on the clarifications of educational design standards, including illustrations and the extent of employment in the educational process, and stressed that the illustrations must be characterized by specific criteria, including: Helping the learner to build knowledge The child and its connection to educational goals and educational content and its focus on the learner as the focus of the learning process, urging the child to practice

thinking processes and encouraging him to do so. Self-learning and stimulating learning develops the ability to observe, make learning interesting, taking into account the mental and psychological levels of students, individual differences. The science book for the first grade of basic education, identifying conflicting fees with learners' goals, contents and levels, and those that are not clear and unrealistic. As well as determining the fees that contradict the principle of non-congestion, then the researcher prepared to analyze the content and verify its validity, and a specialized researcher conducted the analysis on the researcher's side. . The stability of the analysis was confirmed by calculating the coefficient of agreement between the two analysts.

- The percentage of fees that are not in line with the goals (12, 4%)
- Percentage of illustrations that are not important to the topic of the lesson (1%, 27)
- There (23, 3%) of the illustrations do not match the levels of learners.
- The fees are inaccurate, as they amounted to (14.7%)
- There (20, 9%) of the fee is unclear.

Reaching the crowded tariff rate (17, 1%). The researcher continued the necessity of involving specialists in educational technology in designing curricula, re-evaluating the science book for the first grade of basic education, and selecting illustrations according to the required standards and conditions (Muhammad, 2002: 16). Through this, the researcher benefited from the previous studies and considered that her selection of a set of basic criteria according to the scientific picture of the illustrations in the current study, which included (10) important criteria for their importance in the sixth science book. Primary grade are as follows:-

1. The standard of conformity of the content to the scientific image.
2. Scientific accuracysorrow.
3. Match the title of the image.
4. Clarity of the image.
5. Color accuracy.
6. The size of the scientific image.
7. The picture is suitable for the level of students.
8. The modernity of the scientific picture.
9. The type of paper for the scientific image.
10. The shape of the image.

Research Methodology and Procedures

The researcher followed the procedures for the purpose of verifying the goal of her research, which is related to evaluating the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the standards of the scientific image and what includes determining the research method - the research community and its sample - data sources - the research tool and how to prepare it - and to ensure the sincerity and stability of the administration)

Research method

The researcher used the descriptive research method as an appropriate approach for the current study for the purpose of analyzing and evaluating the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the standards of the scientific image because the survey methods are in the descriptive approach, so when should the content analysis identify data sources - and to have a research tool and units of analysis - and enumeration of units - Clear and clear rules for the method of analysis

Research community and sample

A. Research community: it means (a group of events or elements with common characteristics that can be observed and measured) (Maysan Research Journal, 2016: 315)Therefore, the research community included all the pictures and illustrations in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school according to the standards of the scientific image for the academic year (2017 - 2018) and the number (198) pictures or science, but I am clarifying.

B. The research sample: fully represented and represented (book sample)

Choose data sources

The researcher dealt with the analysis process in this research for the purpose of explanatory evaluation in the science book for the sixth primary primary sixth grade with its units according to the standards of the scientific image for the academic year (2017-2018), which consists of (10) criteria, which include (matching the standard content of the scientific image - standard scientific accuracy - matching Image title - image clarity - color accuracy - image size - image appropriate to the level of students - newness of the image - paper quality of the scientific image - image format). Which constitutes an integrated community (Table 1), where the research community is one of the important steps in educational research, which requires great accuracy (Bahri, 2012: 315)

Table (1)

The number of parsed pages	edition	The title of the book
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198	I 2 for the year2017	Science book for the sixth grade of primary
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Research tool (analysis tool)

A tool has been adopted for analyzing and evaluating the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the (scientific image) criteria, which consists of (10) main criteria, Appendix No. (1), prepared by the researcher. Looking at previous research and studies such as the study (Mohammed, 2002) and the study (Al-Barakat, 2008) for the purpose of collecting data accurately and clearly to reach conclusions about the content of the content.

The purpose of the analysis

The analysis process aims to limit the scientific picture or illustration in the science book for the sixth grade according to the criteria mentioned in the list that has been prepared, and to monitor its repetitions, and to identify the scientific images that comply with the standard and which do not conform to the standard. No.

Analysis units

They are the units of content that can be counted or measured to arrive at semantics or stability that help in the interpretation of results. There are some units used in content analysis on which the analysis process is based, namely:

1. The units of record are the smallest part of the analyzed content by which phenomena are calculated. The process of analysis aims to diagnose it, that is, it is the unit in which the repetition of the illustrations in the said book appears.
2. Content units/ that surround the recording units and which should be examined for the purpose of communicating to diagnose the recording units (Al-Tamimi, 2009: 317)
3. Census units / the researcher used repetition as a unit to monitor the census and enumerate all scientific phenomena and illustrations for the purpose of adhering to the criteria used in the current study for the purpose of giving equal weights.

Validity of the analysis

In order to verify the apparent validity of the tool, it was presented to a group of experts and arbitrators in the methods of teaching science, measurement and evaluation in its initial form, Annex (1), and those who have experience in the quality of standards to express their opinions from a linguistic and scientific point of view, and their number is (10) arbitrators in Annex (2)), and thus a list of the researcher's criteria and number (10) criteria for extending the scientific image were returned (1). Taking the opinions of the arbitrators about the validity of the criteria for their importance in the science book for the sixth grade, which was promised (80%) by the experts on the survival of all criteria because it is characterized by an educational transfer for the sixth grade. Experiences, facts and concepts on the minds of primary school students and to ensure the correctness of the analysis and then to evaluate the illustrations in the science book for the sixth grade in English. In parallel with the criteria prepared in the current study, the researcher analyzed a random sample of (scientific images and illustrations) to be evaluated and presented to the arbitrators and agreed with them on the method of analysis to ensure the validity of the analysis. Sample: A percentage of the analyzed material (20%) was taken, that is, (40) pages with pictures and illustrations that included the first unit (object properties). (Al-Hayat Net) from the science book for the sixth grade of primary school.

Stability analysis.

The stability of the instrument (analysis) was verified using Cooper's equation in calculating the reliability coefficient, where the researcher analyzed the first unit (characteristics of living organisms) in the science book for the sixth grade in agreement with the external unit. Analysts specializing in science teaching methods where reliability was extracted in two ways:-

- A. Agreement with time: he conducted an analysis for the same researcher who was chosen randomly, then repeated the process for the same sample after (30) days using Cooper's equation and the stability value (0, 83), which is the value of the appropriate research.
- B. Agreement with external analysts: A random sample was selected from the total population of (198) scientific images and illustrations, and the sample was (20%) with the number (40) images of a sixth-grade scientific book. Including (the first unit) the calculated stability coefficient (0, 81) for the researcher in the first analyzer * and (0, 84) for the researcher in the second analyzer *, (0, 89) between the first and second analyzers, and the stability more than (70%) is considered highly This indicates the stability of the analysis tool (Al-Kubaisi, 2010: 171). Table No. (2) shows the value of the stability coefficients using Cooper's equation.

Table (2)

the value	Style	Stability type
83 , 0	Between the researcher and herself after	agreement over time

	thirty	
81 , 0	Between the researcher and the first analyst	Agreement with external analysts
84 , 0	Between the researcher and the second analyst	
89 , 0	Between the first analyzer and the second analyst	

The value of the stability coefficients of the analysis

1. NS. Dr. Muhammad Khalil / Methods of Teaching Science / College of Basic Education / Al-Mustansiriya University.
2. NS. Dr. Salma Fattah Raheef / Methods of Teaching Science / College of Basic Education / Al-Mustansiriya University.

Statistical means

The researcher used the statistical bag (spss) to get the results as follows

Cooper's equation to calculate the stability of the analysis:

$$\text{Stability coefficient} = \frac{\text{The number of cases of agreement}}{\text{The number of cases of disagreement} + \text{the number of cases of agreement}} \times 100\%$$

Percentage of Frequencies on Evaluation Results (Illustrations)

Section

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{Total summation}}{\text{Total summation}} \times 100\% \text{ (Al Kubaisi, 2010: 171)}$$

Total summation

Presentation and interpretation of results

As for the objective of the research, which included (evaluation of illustrations in the science book for the primary stage according to the scientific picture), the researcher presented the most important results, their interpretation and discussion, and in light of that, recommendations were made and recommendations were made. The results of the current research were reached, which included (10) criteria for the scientific image in the science book for the sixth grade. Basic Annex No. (1) Below presents the most important frequencies and percentages that were reached for each criterion separately, and Table No. (3) Shows the most important results that were reached.

Table (3)Frequencies and percentages of the criterion (matching the content to the scientific picture) in the science book for the sixth grade

percentage	Repetition	Type
7 , 82	96	Content matching with the scientific image
2 , 17	20	It does not match the scientific picture

It is clear from Table No. (3) The presentation of the obtained results, where the frequencies and percentages were calculated for each criterion (the scientific picture) and the illustrations were compared with the assumed percentage (70%) determined by the experts and arbitrators when taking their opinions on the previously mentioned criteria. The first criterion that He obtained a ratio of (82, 7) which is a high percentage for the criterion (content matching the scientific image) for skills and activities. From the science book for the sixth grade of primary school, which are reflected in the illustrations for the purpose of properly conveying information and experiences to male and female students, while the percentage of illustrations that do not match the content is (17, 2)

Table (4)Frequencies and percentages of the standard (scientific accuracy) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
9 , 86	120	good
0 , 13	18	not good

A table showing (4) pictures or illustrations. The number (120) scientific pictures is a ratio of (86, 9) illustrations, clear and good, with a high percentage in the second, third and fourth academic units in the science book. For the sixth grade of primary school, while the poor illustrations got the number of repetitions (18) scientific pictures in the ratio (13, 0) in the science book, ignoring a section for the fifth and sixth school units as the unit scientific accuracy of the picture caption.

Table (5) Frequencies and percentages for the criterion (matching the title to the picture) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
% 70	35	Appropriate
% 30	15	inappropriate

It is clear from Table No. (5) that the scientific illustrations and pictures in the science book for the sixth grade (appropriate) in terms of matching the title for each unit or semester of science subject, included (35) appropriate explanations matching the title and at a rate of (70%). While the illustrations that were not appropriate for the title were (15) scientific images (30%), and this is a small percentage compared to the supposed spoken word (70%), according to the opinions of experts and arbitrators.

Table (6) Frequencies and percentages for the criterion (clarity of the image) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

Percentage	Repetition	Type
5 , 82	118	clear
4 , 17	25	Unclear

Table (6) shows the number of pictures and scientific illustrations that were (clear), especially in the first, second, third and repetitive units (118), while the ratio (82, 5) was high. The ratio while the illustrations obtained (and not clear) in the rest of the study units were given (25) illustrative and the ratio (17, 4)

Table (7) Frequencies and percentages of the criterion (color accuracy) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

Percentage	Repetition	Type
4 , 71	80	good
5 , 28	32	not good

It is clear from Table No. (7) Above the standard (color accuracy) of the scientific picture in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school, where the illustrations are characterized by high accuracy in color and frequency (80). . A picture of scientific illustrations and a ratio (71, 4) while I got (not good) illustrations that are not characterized by color accuracy at a frequency of (32) drawings and a ratio (28, 5), because the colors tend to blue thinking about the educated and educated appearance and the difficulty of understanding the image And what it contains of scientific facts and concepts, etc.

Table (8) Frequencies and percentages of the criterion (the size of the scientific image) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
% 73	73	big
% 27	27	small

Table (8) above shows that the illustrations (large size) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school got re- 7 3) scientific pictures or illustrations by (73%) and this is a good percentage compared to the speakers. The hypothesis agreed upon by the experts, while the illustrations (small size) were repeated (27) explained in the third, fifth and sixth units at a rate of (27%). Small percentage for illustrations.

Table (9) Frequencies and percentages of the criterion (appropriateness of the picture to the level of students) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
1 , 81	69	suitable
8 , 18	16	Inappropriate

It is clear from Table No. (9) that the scientific drawings and pictures are commensurate with the level of the students and prove their acquisition of experience and scientific facts, as the researcher indicated in the illustrations in the Science Book, which was a fair mindset for their level and the acquisition of behavioral and educational goals, they have to repeat (69) scientific pictures in A section of the academic units by (1, 81), which is very good and accurate, while the illustrations (not appropriate).) The students obtained a repetition level of (16) scientific images and a ratio of (18, 8), and this is a very small percentage.

Table (10) frequencies and percentages for the criterion (recentness of the image) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
7 , 71	56	modern
2 , 28	22	An old

Table (10) above shows the modern scientific illustrations and pictures in a six-unit science book. 56 images and scientific explanations must be repeated, and the ratio is (71, 7). As for the pictures and drawings of others (old), the percentage is less (28, 2)

Table (11) Frequencies and percentages of the standard (paper quality of the image) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

Percentage	Repetition	Type
2 , 53	33	good
7 , 46	29	not good

Table (11) shows, illustrations that both types of good papers should be repeated (33) and the percentage (53, 2) which is very low compared to the default by experts and arbitrators, which is (70%).), while I get the illustrations that appear on paper (not good), also on repetition (29) and in (46, 7) which is very small.

Table (12) Frequencies and percentages of the criterion (the figure of the picture) in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school

percentage	Repetition	Type
% 75	135	Horizontal
% 25	45	vertical

Table No. (12) Shows pictures and scientific illustrations in the science book for the sixth grade of primary school, which is characterized by the (horizontal) shape of the image, which received a repetition of (135) in some academic units and with repetition. The percentage is (75%), which is a good percentage. As for the illustrations of the obtained shape (vertical), it is repeated (45) and at a rate of (25%), which is a very low percentage.

Conclusions

Through the research results, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

1. The evaluation of the illustrations in the science book for the primary stage for the sixth grade according to the scientific picture was not at the required level for all (six) units of study compared to the hypothesis made by the arbitrators and experts, which is (70%) any section of the illustrations was in some units and the study was completed And the other section was not within the required level in the standard prepared for the study.
2. The science book for the sixth grade is less interested and includes clarifications that include scientific activities and facts.

Recommendations

In light of the research results, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Reconsidering when printing scientific books by curriculum developers by increasing scientific illustrations and pictures and adding an element of suspense to them to attract the attention of the largest number of male and female learners when teaching.
2. Emphasis on the principle of scientific accuracy and the use of colors. A clear, unprinted diagram that is ambiguous for the purpose of conveying the scientific idea correctly to students.
3. The illustrations should be commensurate with the level of male and female learners in the primary stages.
4. Emphasis on the principle of integration between the topics of books and their integration with all modern scientific activities and illustrations.

Suggestions

In the current study, the researcher suggests the following:

1. Study a similar study of the sciences of the current book and the other stages.
2. Studying the effect of illustrations on the achievement of secondary school students.

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